

SUCCESS STORY OF WATER CONSERVATION AT PLANET GREEN, VADODARA

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ABSTRACT

Water is the ‘elixir of life’ and considered to be the most important natural resource required for the development of any area. The very existence of life is impossible without the availability of water.

With the change in our lifestyles, the per capita consumption of water has been increasing with each passing day. We are now using water in manifolds as compared to our forefathers.

It is now a common knowledge that has also been proved by researchers in the fields of water resources that a water crisis is looming and it is time we think of water conservation and judicious use of water.

Keeping this point in mind, Planet Green – a project of residential units has been designed and planned in such a way that there is maximum conservation, recycling and reuse of water available within the colony.

Planet Green Has Also Been Given The Platinum Rating For Eco Housing Colony.

The paper attempts to share the success story of maximum use of each drop of water which can be taken as an example by other individual projects.

INTRODUCTION

In the entire universe, Earth is the only place where life exists. The mother Earth sustains several living organisms like animals, birds, insects, trees along with human beings. Nature has given special powers to human being which includes power to think what is good and what is bad along with the power of creation. But in the process of creating comforts with the help of development of science and technology, man has been selfish. On his path to progress, mankind has also caused irreparable damage to the natural resources and thus depriving the next generations of several things which we or our fore-fathers have enjoyed without any guilt. This has resulted into several

phenomenons like climate change, ozone layer depletion, global warming, etc to name a few.

It is time now for each one of us to awaken and realize the extent of harm that we are causing to the nature and that it is time for us to make small but effective changes in our day to day life style so that we can atleast prevent further exploitation of natural resources.

Keeping all this in mind and working towards the concept of Green Housing Colonies has resulted in a project called Planet Green at Talsat village on Kalali – Chapad road near Vadodara. The project developers have tried to include several features which justify the name of the project.

SALIENT FEATURES OF PLANET GREEN

Some of the salient features of the project are as follows:

1. The entire plot of the project has a 12 watt 3' high solar base fencing on compound wall. This ensures protection from intruders on 24 hour basis, thereby minimizing the use of individual security.
2. The common plots as well as the internal roads have been provided with L.E.D base street lights. These lights have been fixed at a comparatively low heights for intense and better lights. Further, the streetlights have been placed at 45° on the horizontal plane in opposite lanes rather than being placed parallelly. This ensures optimum utilization of lights and at the same time reduces consumption of energy.
3. A 10 KV solid waste utilization base gasifier has been provided to support common electrical supply.
4. All the individual plots have been provided with a main drainage line with septic tank. The waste water will be treated by an in house treatment plant and the water will be reused for maintaining the plantations of the plot.
5. A Gravity base porous drip irrigation system for plants supported by processed society's drainage water without any mechanical and chemical process. This process ensures that no electricity is used for supplying water to the plantations and at the same time only required quantity of water is used. The results for comparison of porous drip irrigation system as compared to the traditional drip irrigation system have shown significant difference in the growth of the plants.
6. Rain water harvesting and ground water recharging system has been provided for individual plots. An underground water tank for storing the roof top harvested rain water and utilizing it by a small hand pump provided on the kitchen platform has been provided to prevent unnecessary wastage of water due to running taps.
7. The buildings will be constructed using specially designed mud bricks and fly ash bricks. The external walls on the south west have been constructed as cavity walls to prevent excessive heating due to sun.

8. The architectural planning of the building includes features creating air passages. Sleek windows have been provided at the slab level and floor levels on exteriors to ensure cross ventilation and air passage thus minimizing the requirement for provision of air-conditioners.
9. Individual buildings have been provided with solar lights in basic areas like kitchen, passage and drawing room, thus saving electricity.
10. Large windows have been placed and architectural planning is done in a way to utilize maximum sunlight for ambience.
11. Sky lights have been provided in common kitchen to ensure sufficient light during day time too. Lower slab height has been provided on the north east so ensure air drafting and removal of hot air.
12. Swimming pool has been provided with skimmer units thus ensuring sufficient oxidation so as to avoid replacement of the water for a period of 20 years. The swimming pool flooring is typical so as not to encourage weed and fungal growth.
13. Storm water drains have been provided collecting water in an underground sump for utilization at common places as well as providing water supply for plantations in monsoon.
14. Tiles with holes for providing breathing facility for plantations have been used surrounding the trunks of trees.
15. The dried leaves of plantations will be utilized for creating vermin-compost manure or shall be utilized in a biogas plant.
16. Parts of the RCC roads like all cross ways and regions where underground pipes / ducts cross the roads have been constructed using paver blocks to facilitate easy operation and maintenance.

Besides this, there are various recreational amenities and supporting infrastructure provided by the developers so as to improve the living standards of the residents. Some of them have been listed below.

INFRASTRUCTURE

- Main entrance gate in a decorative design.
- External boundary wall in masonry, front side in an exposed brick design.
- Security cabin equipped with boom barrier gate and C.C.T.V. Camera
- Automatic hydro-pneumatic system for Main water supply line for equal water and pressure.
- Provision for corporation C.I. line and provision of ½” P.V.C. connection.
- Provision for telephone, intercom system and cable connection.
- R.C.C. tremix roads with designed paver blocks & landscaping on road sides.
- Underground electrical cables and provision for individual line.

RECREATIONAL AMENITIES

- Large Kitchen and lawn for functions
- Covered Badminton Court

- Two Clay Tennis Courts
- Two covered T.T. Tables
- Gymnasium, Carom, chess, Pool Table, Snooker Table
- Children play equipments and amphitheatre
- Provision for traditional games
- Society's office and provision for library and utility store.
- Swimming pool, Jacuzzi bath, kids and infants pool with changing rooms.
- Two practice cricket nets.
- Practice basketball court.
- Jogging track with four layer plantation.

As water is one of the important elements of our daily consumption, the infrastructure of the project has been designed with an attempt of make optimum utilization of resources by way of recycling and reuse.

WATER CONSERVATION PRACTICES

- In swimming pool

Normally swimming pool water is changed weekly and lakhs litres of water is drained into the sewage. In Planet Green, anti-weed growth lining is provided in the floor of swimming pool. Skimmers are provided for continuous purification of water. For disinfection, chlorine tablets are utilized. As a result, only make up water which is lost in evaporation is added weekly and the entire water of the swimming pool can utilized years together.

- For Plantation

Sowing, manuring, and other farm activities are carried out as per bio-dynamic calendar.

Water supply to the plantations in the colony is done with the help of porous pipes. The water oozes from the micro pores of the pipes depending upon the moisture availability in the soil of root zone of the plant and the water requirement of the plant. It also reduces evaporation losses and weed growth. All the irrigation methods are supply driven. This is the only method which is demand based.

Saw dust is mixed with the soil for increasing water holding capacity of the soil near each plant.

Method of total organic farming has been adopted in the colony. Due to organic farming, water holding capacity of the soil increases. As a result, only 50% watering is required.

Mulching is carried out by dry leaves of trees and dry grass to reduce evapo-transpiration losses.

A groove is provided on the walkway side towards the plantations leading to the supply of water from the storm water drain during the monsoon.

- Daily Activities

A hand pump connection has been provided on the kitchen platform for using the water stored in the underground tank. This has been provided to prevent unnecessary wastage of water due to running taps in kitchen use.

The other utilization of water in the form of car wash or any other such use is planned in such a way that the used water is diverted to the nearby plantations.

- Judicious use of water in common areas

Auto stop taps have been provided to prevent wastage of water in common areas. Water saving is kept in mind while selecting taps and showers for individual houses too.

Wash areas of common buildings have been provided with porous flooring to collect the spilled water. This water is once again diverted to the common sump.

WATER HARVESTING PRACTICES

- Roof top Harvesting

It is mandatory for all the individual plots of the project to provide system for Rain water harvesting. An underground water tank is provided below the dining area of each house. The water collected from the roof tops of the building is stored in this underground tank and utilized for drinking purpose throughout the year.

GROUNDWATER RECHARGING PRACTICES

- Recharge Tube well

A recharge tube well is constructed nearly 10m away from the production bore. Paved area storm water is diverted into the filters and after removing the turbidity from the monsoon water the bore well is recharged. Air vent pipe is provided for the release of air from the aquifer during the recharging.

- Recharge Shafts

Recharge shafts are provided in the storm water drain just outside the compound at every 5m distance. The top 60 cm of the recharge shaft is filled with pebbles to restrict floating debris entry into the recharge shaft. The plantation between the compound wall and storm water drain are taking water from the wet soil around the recharge shaft. So for nearly 6 months of the year, no watering is required.

REUSE OF WATER

Dual pipe system for plumbing of each house is adopted. Sullage and sewage are separated. Sewage leads to a small septic tank. The supernatant liquid after separation of

the solids is connected into the common drainage line. The kitchen and bathroom waste is known as Sullage. The Sullage is directly connected into the common line. The whole premises drainage is stored in a large sump and treated by an in house treatment plant using electrolysis process. The treated water is reused for irrigating through porous pipes the plantations and gardens of the plot.

Rain water drains placed on both the sides of the roads leading to a common sump

Rain water drain connected to the plantations so that it is not necessary to provide water in monsoon.

Low height taps with autostop & stone shield for less wastage of water at common plot

Porous flooring of wash area at common plot with collection facility for keeping the area clean & dry

Sewage treatment by Electrolysis process

Top Closer View of Sewage treatment unit

Weed growth preventive lining in common swimming pool

Four Skimmer units for continuous cleaning of water thus ensuring sufficient oxidation so as to avoid replacement of the water for several years.

Assembly of filter for roof top harvesting

CONCLUSION

Planet Green has set an example for water conservation, harvesting and recharging. Reuse of water has also been done wherever possible. Wind energy, solar energy and solid waste management along with efficient use of electricity has resulted in award of Platinum Rating for the project.

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